

NEWSLETTER

COMPAS_sCO₂

Contents

[Status of Implementation](#)

[COMPAS_sCO₂ Participation at Conferences](#)

[Meetings](#)

[How to Get Involved](#)

APRIL 30, 2023

Issue : V

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action (RIA) under grant agreement No. 958418

Team: 12 partners
from 7 countries

Research focus: New
particles, metal alloys
and heat exchanger

Duration: 1
November 2020 –
31 October 2024

Status of Implementation

Several results, deliverables, milestones have been achieved. All public deliverables and main activities are freely accessible through the project's website: <https://www.compassco2.eu/>. The section below summarizes the status of project activities by work package.

WP2 – DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF PARTICLES

Saint-Gobain has finalized the development of a novel particle type composed of a mix of different oxides. The particles are produced via the granulation process and make use of recycled waste products from the steel industry. Hence, low prices of around 1€ per kg can be achieved. Four generations of particles have been produced, fine-tuning composition and optimizing their properties. At the end of the development within COMPASSCO₂, the specific heat capacity at 1000°C has been improved along with the density whilst matching the mechanical resistance of the state-of-the-art bauxite particles. The drawback of the novel particles is their low solar absorptance of 83% (around 1-7% lower compared to different

bauxite-based particle types). However, the herein developed coatings from CIEMAT, DFI and DLR can boost the solar absorptance of the granulated Gen. 4 particles up to 98%.

Granulated Generation 1 to 3 particles have already shown excellent stability under thermal aging at 1000°C for up to 4000 hours in a muffle furnace, outperforming the state-of-the-art bauxite particles. Testing of Gen. 4 particles with and without coatings is currently ongoing. In addition, the attrition rate will be examined in the novel high-temperature erosion test bench shown in figure below. In parallel, the mechanical modelling tailored to the specific particle compositions is ongoing to predict mechanical wear and attrition.

Figure: Left) Setup to examine attrition or erosion caused by falling hot particles. The particles are pre-heated in the upper furnace and impact on the target material located in the lower furnace with a speed of around 5 m/s. Both furnaces will be set to 900°C. Right) Cross section of coated Gen. 4 particle with chemical composition map determined by EDX.

WP5 – TECHNOLOGY VALIDATION

The fabrication and assembly of the experimental facility for particle heating is nearly finished (figure right). The purpose of this facility is to validate the proposed technology for heating the particles, where the temperature limit was set to 800°C, as well as the air/particles transportation system that enables the particle mass-flow control and its circulation. Furthermore it will be possible to evaluate the heat transfer coefficient on the particle side. The particles mass-flow is controlled by displacing its volume by screw conveyor (shown in figure down), which was fabricated from Nimonic® Alloy 80A to withstand its operating conditions. In the first stage, the whole system was tested and tuned at the cold state and the mass-flow characteristics were measured. In the following stage the heater rods will be assembled and the whole facility will be thermally insulated to perform the heating experiments.

Figure: Fabricated conveying screw – material – Nimonic Alloy 80A.

Figure: Experimental facility for particle heating.

WP7 – COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION

Within the framework of WP7, regular updates have been ensured through the different COMPASCO₂ communication and dissemination tools, including the [project website](#), [zenodo](#) and social media accounts ([linkedin](#) and [twitter](#)). Several activities are ongoing, including:

- A **webinar** on primary heat exchangers, organized in cooperation with other EU and nationally funded research projects under the coordination of ETN Global in June 2023,
- The **Second Stakeholders workshop**, organized back-to-back with the High Temperature Corrosion and Oxidation 2023 workshop (25-29 September 2023 in Marktheidenfeld, Germany).

In addition to **oral presentations** delivered at different conferences in the beginning of this year (see next section), several others are foreseen, including:

- *Ab initio* study on the effect of alloying elements for Cr-based superalloys toward next generation concentrated solar power, at Euro Nano Forum, by VTT.

- *New ceramic media for Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) Plants*, at ECERS 2023, by SGCREE.
- *High temperature oxidation and erosion behaviour of candidate materials for concentrated solar power plants with ceramic particles and CO₂ heat-transfer systems*, at the High Temperature Corrosion and Oxidation 2023 workshop, by FZJ.

Four **scientific papers** are also in preparation, including:

- *Variability and associated uncertainty in image analysis for soiling characterization in solar energy systems*, by DLR.
- *Design of novel Cr-Ni-Al-Fe chromium-based bcc-superalloys: Iron supplements for strength and thermal stability* by UoB.
- *Accurate identification and measurement of the precipitate area by two-stage deep neural networks in novel chromium-based alloys*, by UoB.
- *Heat exchangers for concentrated solar thermal power plants with particle receiver and a s-CO₂ Brayton cycle: Tube material selection*, by DFI.

COMPASsCO₂ Participation at Conferences

COMPASsCO₂ results presented at MRS 2023, April 10-14, 2023

Presentation - Material candidates for the heat exchanger tubes for solar sCO₂ Brayton cycles. In this presentation, the material selection criteria for the COMPASsCO₂ heat exchanger tubes is summarized, the first results of the mechanical properties at high temperature of commercial alloys are discussed as well as the development of novel Cr nickel aluminide (NiAl) and Cr silicides superalloys. The presentation was delivered by Marta Serrano (CIEMAT).

Presentation - Advances in Optical Coating Materials for CST. Within the COMPASsCO₂ project, the integration of particle systems into highly efficient-CO₂ Brayton power cycles for electricity production is pursued. These particles are coated with black coatings to increase their solar absorptance and withstand high temperatures. In general, the big challenge is the development of coatings with both high optical properties and high durability at

operation conditions. In this talk, the advances in the development of optical coatings applied in components of CST as well as the development in characterization protocols were presented. The presentation was given by Gema San Vicente (CIEMAT).

CIEMAT colleagues at the 2023 MRS Conference

COMPASsCO₂ results presented at TMS 2023, March 19-23, 2023

THE WORLD COMES HERE.
TMS 2023
152nd Annual Meeting & Exhibition

Presentation - Chromium-Silicon Alloys with Iron and Nickel for Structural High Temperature Applications. The work presented investigates the effect of alloying Cr-Si-alloys with the elements Fe and Ni and targets the microstructure and precipitation of A15 phase. Ni can cause the effect of solution softening in Cr and increases the low-temperature ductility as a result. For Fe it is shown, that it stabilizes the two-phase structure consisting of nitration resistant A15 phase and Crss. Oxidation exposures at 1200°C in synthetic air indicate that Fe additions up to 5 at.% increase also the nitridation resistance of

Crss. The [presentation](#) was delivered by Mathias Galetz (DFI).

Presentation - Chromium-based bcc-Superalloys Tailored by Iron Addition. The presentation shows the results of the chromium-based bcc-superalloys tailored by iron addition. In particular, the results demonstrate the advantageous ageing behaviour of Cr superalloys compared to ferritic superalloys and nickel-based superalloys. The Fe-enhanced Cr-superalloys exhibit high hardness of ~500 HV0.5, dominated by solid-solution and precipitate strengthening mechanisms. Microstructure tailoring with Fe additions offers a new design pathway to improve the balance of properties in Cr-superalloys and so accelerate their development for high temperature applications. It was presented by Kan Ma (UoB).

Poster - Mechanical Testing of Novel Chromium Superalloys Strengthened by Intermetallic Precipitates. It presents the results of mechanical testing of novel chromium superalloys, given that high melting point, low costs and oxidation/corrosion resistance, strengthened by intermetallic precipitates. The

results from high temperature compression tests of chromium nickel aluminides, benchmarked against state-of-the-art materials, and used to provide an estimate for the Ductile to Brittle Transition Temperature (DBTT) was presented by Tom Blackburn (UoB).

COMPASsCO₂ results presented at MRS 2022, November 27- December 2, 2022

Presentation - Bcc-Superalloys: bcc refractory metals reinforced by ordered-bcc intermetallic precipitates. In this talk, opportunities for bcc-superalloys systems were discussed, from binaries to ternaries and more complex alloys, including Refractory High Entropy Superalloys. The latest developments in tungsten-based bcc-superalloys, beta-Ti superalloys and chromium superalloys were

also discussed. Prospectives would be given for the onward development of the bcc-superalloy concept for application in nuclear fusion, Gen-IV fission, gas turbines and concentrated solar power. The presentation was delivered by Alexander Knowles (UoB).

COMPASsCO₂ presented at 8as JoRNADAS Corrosão e Proteção de Materiais 2022

Presentation - Thermal Energy Storage and Corrosion at High Temperatures. Selection of cost-efficient structural materials with adequate creep strength and corrosion resistance is one of the most challenging aspects for the design

and operation of concentrated solar power (CSP) plants. This study investigates the corrosion resistance of Fe- and Ni-based alloys in nitrate and chloride salt melts for state-of-the-art systems with thermal energy storage using molten salts, as well as the creep strength and wear resistance of alloys for the next generation particle based systems operating a Brayton sCO₂ cycle. The presentation was delivered by Ceyhun Oskay (DFI).

Meetings

Fourth General Assembly Meeting – The Fourth GA Meeting took place on November 30th and December 1st, 2022 in Plataforma Solar de Almeria (PSA), Tabernas, Spain, hosted by DLR and CIEMAT. This was the first physical GA meeting since the inception of COMPASsCO₂. The COMPASsCO₂ team

discussed the overall progress, on-going activities, challenges, and next steps. In addition to the project meeting, two technical visits were organized: on November 29th the group visited the Andasol-3 power plant, located in Aldeire (Granada), and on November 30th a visit of the Plataforma Solar de Almeria (PSA) facilities.

COMPASsCO₂ Partners attending the project meeting at PSA

Fifth General Assembly Meeting – The 5th project meeting will be hosted by the partner Forschungszentrum Jülich and will take place on June 6th – 7th, 2023 in Jülich, Germany. It will discuss the overall progress, on-going activities, challenges, and next steps. Four technical visits to FZJ, DLR's Synlight, Solar Tower Jülich and laboratories at DLR's Material Research Institute are also scheduled.

Quarterly Phone Conference Meetings - The Quarterly phone call took place on February 22nd, 2023. It discussed the key results and inputs for the different work-packages and any problems/delays/deviations.

Dedicated WP Meetings – Several dedicated WP meetings were organized to discuss the technical aspects of the project with involved partners.

Meeting with other research consortium - On Friday, April 21st, 2023, the CVR was visited by Rafael Guede, a professor at the Swedish

University of KTH and the coordinator of the H2020 SOLARSCO2OL project. The visit was hosted by Otakar Frýbort, leader of work package 5, with his team. The main topics discussed were energy storage and the development of sCO₂ energy cycles. Synergies of ongoing projects, intersections of research areas of interest were also identified and possibilities for future cooperation were discussed.

CVR team with SOLARSCO2OL project coordinator

How to Get Involved in COMPASsCO₂ Activities

Become a member of the project's stakeholders' network

Whether you want to learn more about specific WP activities, collaborate with the consortium or act as an external expert, kindly contact us at contact@compassco2.eu. We will keep you updated about project activities, invite you to attend the project's public events and ask your feedback on the progress and main outcomes of the project.

Check our website and follow us on social media networks

LinkedIn

<https://www.compassco2.eu/>

THANK YOU

For more information

Check the project's website: www.compassco2.eu

Contact us: contact@compassco2.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action (RIA) under grant agreement No. 958418.